

Differences in Problem Solving Behaviours Across Learner Groups

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Abstract. Educational technology research remains overwhelmingly focused on people who live in western, educated, industrialized, rich, and democratic (WEIRD) nations. This assumes that how people learn is independent of local norms. We used data that had been collected through LabintheWild (LitW) to learn about how people solve problems. We analyzed participant solution paths and time-use patterns. Our results showed differences in time-taken per step across groups when solving problems, indicating a need to vary learning supports or materials based on learner background and habits.

Keywords: problem solving, implicit learning, learner background.

1 Introduction

Online learning has become common worldwide [1]. However, as educational resources are exported, they fail because content can be inaccessible across cultures [2] and practices may not translate well. Students may also exhibit biases towards performing certain types of learning activities that are associated with their country of origin [3]. The lack of instructional design guidelines that are specific to various national and cultural contexts is not surprising since the literature remains overwhelmingly focused on people who live in western, educated, industrialized, rich, and democratic (WEIRD) nations [4-5].

Understanding the performance of diverse learners is imperative to developing appropriate curricula and materials for members of different groups. We analysed data collected via the LabintheWild (LitW) online study platform, which has a user base that is empirically less WEIRD [6], to detect patterns in user activities, errors, and the paths they took to solve problems. Through this study, we explored opportunities for providing insight relevant to the development of effective curricula and support materials for students with diverse backgrounds.

2 Literature Review

As argued in sociocultural theory, people learn from their interactions with their environments and those around them [7]. There is also evidence that students from different sociocultural origins learn differently [8]. Thus, analyzing user activities through this framing provides form to the patterns and differences in user performance.

Learning is constrained by student readiness and practice where learning will continue if the result of an action is satisfactory and become challenging when the result is unsatisfactory [7]. This applies both when learners are receiving direct instruction and when they are engaged in implicit learning. Implicit learning is “a process of identifying associations in an environment and storing this information in the form of abstract representations” [9]. This process occurs outside of conscious awareness [10]. For instance, people can learn a category label by encountering it once in a sufficiently rich context [11] or they may need increased exposure to the label over time and in varied contexts [12-13].

While prior work [14] collected data on content sequencing for culturally diverse learners, it did not investigate potential differences across groups. One study focused on techniques for developing instructional procedures that will be accessible and cater to the needs of learners from Latin America [15]. This research highlighted the need for community colleges to embrace culturally inclusive curricula, especially in technology-enhanced education. It cast doubt on the dominant western, efficiency-oriented curriculum and argued that a more holistic approach representative of non-western worldviews should be included. The paper argued that curriculum and content should be globally inclusive and considerate of diverse cultural influences on learning.

3 Methods

We analysed archival data from a between-subjects study of curriculum sequencing approaches [14]. Data was collected through LitW. The study was conducted in English between December 2018 and January 2022. We analyzed this data to explore differences in learner behaviour across population groups.

3.1 The Game Problems and Curricula

The Witness is a game that contains problems the user must solve in the absence of direct instruction. Users are expected to learn the rules for solving different types of problems through trial and error. This makes games from the Witness an interesting space for exploring curriculum in the context of implicit learning.

The original study considered learner responses to different curricula. Each curriculum was composed of 9 problems that the learner had to solve. For 3 of the 5 curricula, the only difference was the sequence in which learners were exposed to problems that had been designed by a human. For the other 2 curricula, problems were automatically selected from the space of all possible problems using Levin Tree Search [14].

The problems we used required participants to divide two groups of dots according to their colour (blue and black) by drawing a line through the dots, which is an NP-hard problem [16]. The dots were organized on a grid and the user was given a start and end position. See Fig. 1 for examples. Squares were the major problem state feature. Squares could have a dot of either colour or no dot. Problems could have between 3 and 16 squares, and there were at most 4 available directions in which a user could draw the boundary line. This resulted in 1,211,178 different potential problem-solution states.

Fig. 1. Sample problems and solutions

3.2 Participants

A total of 1,339 participants consented to their data being used. Consent was obtained prior to starting the study and could be withdrawn near the end of the study. Participants were not compensated.

Participants were relatively young ($M = 25.25$, $SD = 11.67$) and their reported genders reasonably balanced (469 - Male; 447 - Female; 30 - Other; 393 - declined to answer). More than 62% of participants had some post-secondary education (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Participants' highest level of education

Of the 55% who provided their country of residence, 266 were in the USA and 464 were mostly in countries in Europe, Asia, and the Americas. Given representation and participant numbers, a simplifying approach was taken where participants were coded as primarily residing in a WEIRD ($n = 649$) or non-WEIRD ($n = 91$; ~20%) country. Consistent with this national diversity, 32 first languages were reported: English was the most represented ($n = 938$), Swedish had the second-most speakers ($n = 64$), and Brazilian Portuguese had the third-most speakers ($n = 51$).

3.3 Data

The original study collected demographic data and behavioural data as people solved problems. We only analyzed data from those who provided demographic information ($n = 740$). We sampled participant age, gender, and first language; whether they had lived in more than one country; and which country they had lived in the longest.

The problem-solving data had 12,600 observations because many participants chose to retry a problem when their first attempt was unsuccessful. Participants made at least 1 attempt at solving the problem and at most 22 attempts ($M = 9$, $SD = 4.6$).

From the behavioural performance data, we sampled:

- The number of times they reset the problem to its original state.
- The user's first move.
- The time at which they started a problem.
- An array of values that characterizes the line that represents the proposed user solution.
- The problem description (position of the dots that need to be separated).
- Whether a problem was solved correctly.
- The start position for a problem.
- The end position for a problem.

3.4 Data Coding and Analysis Procedures

Participant countries were assigned the WEIRD label when the country was listed as belonging to the Western World [17] and considered educated (> 0.5) according to the world education ranking index [18]. It also had to be industrialized [17]. Countries were considered rich if their gross national income placed them in the upper-middle income group or above [19]. To be considered democratic, the country had to be listed in the world population census as practicing democracy [20] - their index had to be greater than 6.0. This index accounts for multiculturalism in electoral processes, civil rights, an operational government, participation in political processes, and political culture. To be labelled WEIRD, the country had to meet all of the above criteria. The associated repository contains the list of countries by category¹.

We employed KModes [21] to identify problem setting combinations, as defined using the above-listed features. KModes determines dissimilarities between data points

¹ https://github.com/EdTeKLA/ProblemSolvingDifferences_WEIRD_NonWEIRD

by using mode values, making it a more fitting choice for the categorical data we were analyzing.

Data were grouped by participant. The problem states were encoded using integers that represented the locations of the dividing line and filled squares. These problem states were input to KModes. We employed the elbow method to identify the optimal number of clusters that KModes could generate from our dataset. We found 7 clusters.

4 Results

The percentage of participants who resided in WEIRD countries and had lived in more than one country ranged from 20-24% across clusters; most often the other country was also WEIRD or a former colony of their country of residence. The percentage of those who had lived in more than one country but who resided in a non-WEIRD country ranged from 39-56%; most often one of the other countries was European or North American.

The number of moves used to solve a problem by participants residing in WEIRD countries ($M = 9.2$, $SD = 4.5$, $Min = 1$, $Max = 19$) was similar to that of those in Non-WEIRD countries ($M = 9.4$, $SD = 4.8$, $Min = 1$, $Max = 22$). Fig. 3 shows the number of moves performed within each cluster of game states. Based on the figure, clusters can be classified into three categories according to the proportion of users who performed a number of distinct moves: clusters where a specific number of moves was dominant (1, 2, 6, and 7), clusters where there was a wide variety of number of moves (3 and 5), and a cluster that shared both characteristics (4).

Fig. 3. Proportion of participants who performed different numbers of moves by cluster

Fig. 4 shows that at least 150 users were in each of these 7 clusters and that the proportion of participants in non-WEIRD to WEIRD countries was ~10% for each cluster. This suggests that people from different countries will experience similar solution states, as might be expected given the nature of the problem and the constraints of a correct solution.

To better understand the patterns underlying these groupings, we conducted additional analyses that focused on (1) the time taken to complete frequent moves for the clusters where most users employed the same number of moves and (2) the number of moves used in clusters 2 and 5 where there was more variability in user behaviour. Cluster 4 was included in both analyses since it shared characteristics with the other two cluster groupings.

Fig. 4. Proportion of participants residing in WEIRD and non-WEIRD countries by cluster

4.1 Patterns in Time Spent

For clusters with a dominant number of moves, we compared the amount of time spent solving the puzzles with the same number of moves across groups. Fig. 5 displays the time spent for each step made by participants in WEIRD and Non-WEIRD countries. From this, we can see many similarities and some differences in the shapes of the distributions across groups. There was no difference in total time across groups ($U = 8241$, $p = .296$, $r = .02$).

Fig. 5. Time spent in milliseconds (M and SD) by move by group

A Mann Whitney U test indicated that those who resided in WEIRD countries used a little less time to complete their first move ($U = 5430.5$, $p = .048$, $r = .03$). Visual inspection of clusters 1, 7, and, to a lesser extent, 6 shows a downward trend in time spent per move that suggests those in the Non-WEIRD group tended to use more time on their first move while the time use of those in the WEIRD group was more uniform.

4.2 Patterns in Number of Moves Used

We considered the distribution of the top 10 number of moves for the clusters where participants employed a varied number of moves: clusters 3, 5, and 4. In all three clusters, the median was higher for those residing in Non-WEIRD countries than that observed for those in WEIRD countries. These findings suggest there is a group of non-WEIRD participants who used more moves to solve problems. The fact that participants used a different number of moves to solve a problem indicates that they may have approached the problem-solving process differently. It also suggests that Non-WEIRD users, in these groups, may have explored the problem space more instead of pre-planning. Variability was also higher among the Non-WEIRD users in clusters 3 and 5 (see IQR in Table 1), suggesting a greater diversity of approaches among members of this smaller and more diverse group.

Table 1. Distribution of the most common number of user moves

Cluster		Mdn	Min	Max	IQR	Users (#)
3	WEIRD	31	20	54	10.5	163
	Non-WEIRD	56	20	219	45.75	18
4	WEIRD	8	3	34	7.5	268
	Non-WEIRD	11	3	26	6.5	29
5	WEIRD	17	9	35	8	245
	Non-WEIRD	30.5	9	88	34	23

5 Discussion and Conclusion

People who can solve a puzzle in the same number of steps likely have similar levels of implicit knowledge about the task. Consequently, differences in how they manage their time across solution steps suggest differences in how they approach problem solving. By analyzing the time participants spent on problem moves, we identified distinct problem-solving approaches across population groups. For some groupings of solution states, participants in Non-WEIRD countries tended to take more time on early moves and moved more quickly as they progressed through the problem. This could be because members of this group invested more time in planning, extending their initial actions and improving the efficiency of subsequent moves. Looking at the patterns in time taken per step (Fig. 5) also shows some similarities in how time was used across groups. For example, in cluster 2, both groups used more time on step 3. This suggests that they encountered a challenge mid-way through solving their assigned problems. We then see a sharper decline in the amount of time taken by participants in Non-WEIRD

countries; this reduction in time on subsequent steps is consistent with that seen near the beginning of problem solving for participants in Non-WEIRD countries from other clusters. The time use observed in cluster 3 further suggests that the difference in potential early planning holds across groups and that they engage in additional planning when their initial plan fails in some way.

Like with time taken per step, there appeared to be differences between groups for the number of steps used to solve problems. The higher median number of moves suggests that participants in Non-WEIRD countries engaged in more exploration of the potential solution state. The higher interquartile range for number of moves from a subset of these participants also suggests that their approach varies more than that taken by participants in WEIRD countries. Of potential interest is the lack of difference in the central tendency and variability of number of moves for cluster 4. The time and number of moves used by participants who were assigned to this cluster seemed more consistent across population groups, which suggests that there are people who use similar strategies when solving problems independent of their enculturation into specific WEIRD settings. The behaviours of participants in this cluster could also be reflective of the multicultural experiences of some participants. The identified differences and similarities suggest potential biases in curricula design that could differentially benefit the implicit learning process of learners who have different backgrounds. This need for providing alternative methods to access learning opportunities reflects recommendations from large online courses, where different patterns in student use of learning resources were observed [3].

The support for alternative approaches to learning can and should be more nuanced than was possible here because our simple classifications of learner background risk essentializing learners rather than providing nuanced representations of their enculturation and background. The analyses, however, provided more nuanced representations of learner behaviours and sensemaking processes that can be used to support adaptation independently of information about learner background. More nuanced characterizations of learner processes, enculturation, and knowledge are possible through learner models and systems that rely on artificial intelligence to support learning. However, we may need to reframe how we model student learning and how we develop educational technologies to make this more nuanced and personalized support possible.

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